

The Factors Influencing Supply Chain Performance in Tanzanian Public Procuring Entities: The Mediating Role of Supplier-Buyer Relationships

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Abstract:

Academia's current emphasis on supply chain performance highlights the significance of information sharing as a mediator and the supplier-buyer relationship as a moderator. Nevertheless, the examination into the intermediate effects of the supplier-buyer relationship has been relatively neglected. This research examined the factors affecting supply chain performance, emphasizing the mediating role of the supplier-buyer relationship to address the existing knowledge gap in the literature. The research included both descriptive and explanatory methodologies. The positivist research paradigm and stratified sampling method were employed to obtain a sample size of 167 respondents. The data were collected through a

questionnaire and an analysis of relevant documents. The collected data was examined using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling, facilitated by SmartPLS 4, a tool for conducting inferential statistical analysis. The analyzed data on respondents' profiles underwent descriptive statistical analysis using IBM SPSS Statistics Version 26. The research findings indicate that supply chain performance is affected by information sharing, strategic procurement planning, and the relationship between suppliers and buyers. The statistical significance of strategic procurement planning and information sharing indicates that buyers and suppliers rely on these practices to improve supply chain performance. The results provide definitive evidence validating the accuracy of the proposed research model within the domain of decision-making, specifically regarding the prioritization of investments to improve supply chain performance.

Keywords: *Information Sharing, Strategic Procurement Planning, Supplier-Buyer Relationship, Supply Chain Performance.*

Introduction

The phenomenon of globalization has transformed the sourcing function from a local and operational work into a more strategic and unrestricted activity (Nkrumah et al., 2019; Shatta et al., 2024a). This activity is now recognized as an essential element of the company's product offering (Asa et al., 2023). Companies should shift from occasional, one-off supplier relationships to long-term, cooperative partnerships with the aim of building shared values between the consumer and the vendor (Nkrumah et al., 2019; Shatta et al., 2024b). To attain operational excellence, companies must enhance their global-level interactions with suppliers and buyers (Nkrumah et al., 2019). Organizations should strengthen their relationships with suppliers and buyers to get competitively priced goods and services of superior quality. A positive connection between the two entities may also result in enhanced confidence, faster response times, and improved correspondence (Asa et al., 2023).

The competitiveness of supply chain operations is intensified in a dynamic business environment (Shahadat et al., 2023; Corboş et al., 2023; Nwaguru et al., 2022). Hence, it is vital to cultivate supply chain skills to attain a competitive edge and augment the overall performance of the supply chain (Shahadat et al., 2023). On the other hand, strategic procurement strategy is essential for shaping the relationship between suppliers and buyers (Corboş et al., 2023). Likewise, the study by Nwaguru et al. (2022) suggests that implementing strategic procurement techniques, such as fostering trust, engaging in strategic cooperation, and investing in supplier growth, may greatly enhance the efficiency of outsourcing in businesses. Furthermore, research has shown that the execution of strategic procurement 4.0 strengthens the connection between the variables under investigation, resulting in enhanced competitiveness, particularly in the context of the circular economy (Corboş et al., 2023).

Moreover, the use of efficient supplier relationship management (SRM) methods, as a

component of strategic procurement planning, may optimize operational efficiency in public procurement, resulting in enhanced organizational performance (Nwaguru et al., 2022). Hence, by using Supplier Relationship Management (SRM), companies may better their connections with suppliers and buyers, leading to cost-effective products, greater service quality, increased confidence, faster response times, and improved communication (Asa et al., 2023). Similarly, the research conducted by Asa et al. (2023) affirms that strategic procurement planning has an impact on supply chain performance because by implementing strategic sourcing methods, such as staff training, performance evaluation, strategic planning, and supplier relationship management, is strongly correlated with increased company productivity. In addition, the study by Asa et al. (2023) highlights the significance of transitioning from transactional supplier relationships to collaborative, enduring partnerships in order to establish mutual value between buyers and suppliers

Likewise, the research findings from the previous study indicate that information sharing plays a significant role in influencing the supplier-buyer relationship (Kim et al., 2022; Park & Lee, 2018). For example, the study by Park and Lee (2018) emphasizes that information sharing between buyers and suppliers is crucial for enhancing relationship performance, competitiveness, and overall effectiveness. Furthermore, Kim et al. (2022) highlight that information sharing, along with capability-trust between a buyer and its supplier, positively impacts the buyer's relationship performance. Another study emphasizes that information sharing, trust, cooperation, and flexibility are essential determinants of supplier-buyer relationship competitiveness (Park & Lee, 2018). Similarly, buyer-supplier relationship integration is associated with non-financial performance, information sharing in the innovation perspective shows a positive association with suppliers' non-financial performance, highlighting the impact of relationship dynamics on supplier performance within the supply chain (Joensuu-Salo & Sorama,

2019). The supplier-buyer relationship, characterized by factors such as information sharing, trust, cooperation, and integration, plays a vital role in shaping supply chain performance by influencing competitiveness, partnership formation, relationship performance, and supplier performance within the supply chain ecosystem (Owot et al., 2023).

However, the present emphasis in academia on supply chain performance highlights the need of information sharing as a mediator and supplier - buyer relationship as a moderator (bin Aqdas et al., 2023; Ojha et al., 2022; Al-Shboul, 2023). Nevertheless, the study on the mediating effect of the supplier-buyer relationship has been slightly neglected. Furthermore, there is a shortage of empirical research examining the factors that influence supply chain performance via the relationship between suppliers and buyers (Suhaimi et al., 2024, Shatta, 2024). This study aimed to fill the existing knowledge gap in the literature by using the Resource-Based View (RBV) paradigm as its foundation.

Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

The study adopted the Resource-Based View (RBV) theory because it has a significant influence on understanding and enhancing supply chain performance, as evidenced by the previous studies of different context (Sahu et al., 2024; Sharma et al., 2022; Yuen et al., 2019). These studies highlight how the RBV theory is instrumental in identifying critical success factors, evaluating proactive supply chain practices, and understanding the relationships between various factors that influence and enhance overall supply chain performance. For example, the study by Yuen et al. (2019) applied RBV theory to identify critical success factors (CSFs) in the container shipping industry that positively correlate with supply chain integration (SCI) and subsequently with supply chain performance (SCP).

By utilizing RBV theory, the study identifies key resources and capabilities necessary for successful SCI in container shipping firms,

thereby contributing to both theoretical understanding and practical implications for improving supply chain performance (Yuen et al., 2019). Another study examined the effect of lean-green practices and green human resource management on supply chain performance. This research adopted RBV to explore the influence of various factors such as supply chain collaboration, knowledge, information sharing, green human resources management, and lean-green practices on supply chain performance. By employing RBV in the study design and analysis, the research provides insights into how these proactive practices impact supply chain performance and competence (Sahu et al., 2024).

In addition, the study by Sharma et al. (2022) examined the impact of supplier visibility on sustainable practices and supply chain performance during the COVID-19 pandemic using a contingent RBV. The research demonstrates how information sharing with customers and suppliers, along with supply chain traceability, influences visibility, which in turn affects sustainable practices and supply chain velocity, ultimately impacting supply chain performance. By applying RBV in a contingent manner, the study sheds light on the complex relationships between visibility, sustainable practices, and performance in supply chains (Sharma et al., 2022). However, based on the results of the previous studies, this study wanted to know if the act of engaging in strategic procurement planning, sharing information, and fostering a strong relationship between suppliers and buyers would have a valuable influence on the supply chain performance by applying RBV.

The Influence of Strategic Procurement Planning on Supply Chain Performance

The effect of strategic procurement planning on supply chain performance is significant, as evidenced by the research findings from various prior studies. For example, the study by Nkrumah et al. (2019) assert that strategic sourcing practices, including employee learning, performance, planning, and supplier relational processes are key factors influencing firm productivity. The study emphasizes the positive and significant relationship between strategic

sourcing and firm productivity, highlighting the importance of strategic sourcing in enhancing overall organizational performance (Nkrumah et al., 2019). In the context of construction projects, the study by Masanta and Ochiri (2016) emphasizes that the supply chain management practices are influenced by inventory management, supplier selection, strategic purchasing, and procurement planning. The study indicates that effective procurement planning, supplier evaluation, and inventory management positively impact the performance of construction projects, underscoring the role of strategic procurement practices in enhancing project outcomes (Masanta & Ochiri, 2016). However, strategic procurement planning, which includes techniques for managing relationships with suppliers, is essential for improving supply chain performance and overall organizational success (Asa et al., 2023). Furthermore, the act of strategically planning procurement has a direct effect on the relationship between the supplier and buyer. It promotes trust, cooperation, and development, which in turn affects the efficiency of operations, competitiveness, and overall performance of the organization (Asa et al., 2023).

Based on the results of the previous literature (Nkrumah et al., 2019; Masanta & Ochiri, 2016; Asa et al., 2023), this study predicted that strategic procurement planning would positively influence the supplier-buyer relationship and the supply chain performance.

H_{1a}: Strategic procurement planning positively and directly influences supplier-buyer relationship

H_{1b}: Strategic procurement planning positively and indirectly influences supply chain performance through supplier-buyer relationship

The Influence of Information Sharing on Supply Chain Performance

The effect of information sharing on supply chain performance has been studied extensively in various contexts. For example, the study by Baah et al. (2021) revealed that information sharing positively and significantly influences supply chain visibility, collaboration, agility, and performance. Supply chain visibility,

collaboration, and agility, in turn, have significant impacts on supply chain performance. The study emphasizes the critical role of information sharing in enhancing competitive gains and superior supply chain performance (Baah et al., 2021). Another study by bin Aqdas et al. (2023) found that proper, timely, and accurate exchange of information between an enterprise and its suppliers can lead to improved order fulfillment rates, reduced costs, and increased supply chain performance. The study highlights the importance of managing information effectively to mitigate the bullwhip effect and strengthen partner relationships for better supply chain integration (bin Aqdas et al., 2023).

Likewise, Alhamda et al. (2023) revealed that information sharing has a positive effect on supply chain performance, mediated by company relationships. This study specifically highlights the positive impact of information sharing on supply chain performance through company relationships (Alhamda et al., 2023). Effective information sharing practices can lead to superior gains, competitiveness, flexibility, and improved overall supply chain performance. The integration of information sharing and buyer-supplier relationship positively affects suppliers' non-financial performance (Joensuu-Salo & Sorama, 2019). In addition, research shows that information sharing and integration in buyer-supplier relationships can affect suppliers' performance positively, particularly in terms of non-financial aspects (Joensuu-Salo & Sorama, 2019). The study by Park and Lee (2018) also revealed that information sharing is a key factor that influences the dynamics of the supplier-buyer relationship by fostering trust, cooperation, competitiveness, and overall performance. Information sharing within and between firms, along with support aimed at supplier development, are significant factors for improving a buyer's performance, although their effects on firm performance may vary (Carr & Kaynak, 2007). Information sharing and integration in a buyer-supplier relationship can positively influence suppliers' non-financial performance, indicating a link between information sharing and supplier performance

within the supply chain (Joensuu-Salo & Sorama, 2019). Information sharing and capability-trust between a buyer and its supplier have a positive impact on the buyer's relationship performance, emphasizing the importance of information exchange in enhancing relationship dynamics (Park & Lee, 2018). Information sharing, facilitated by the capacity for social exchange in buyer-supplier relationships, positively influences knowledge sharing and innovation speed within the supply chain, highlighting the role of information exchange in driving innovation and competitiveness (Ojha et al., 2022).

Information sharing and capability-trust between a buyer and its supplier have a direct effect on the buyer's relationship performance. This indicates that fostering information exchange and trust can lead to improved performance within the supply chain (Park & Lee, 2018). Based on the findings of prior literature, this study hypothesized that information sharing would positively influence supplier-buyer relationship and the supply chain performance.

H_{2a}: Information sharing positively and directly influences supplier-buyer relationship

H_{2b}: Information sharing positively and indirectly influences supply chain performance through supplier-buyer relationship

The Influence of Supplier-Buyer Relationship on Supply Chain Performance

The effect of the supplier-buyer relationship on supply chain performance has been examined in the previous studies. For example, the study by Khan et al. (2022) evaluates the impact of uncertainty, supplier involvement, supplier performance, and partnership quality on buyer dependence on the supplier. It reveals that early supplier involvement, partnership quality, and supplier performance have a significant and positive influence on buyer dependence. Effective management should consider these factors to increase buyer dependency on suppliers (Khan et al., 2022). This research focuses on the manufacturing industry and explores the effect of buyer-supplier partnership

and information integration on supply chain performance. The study emphasizes that trust and guanxi play a crucial role in sustaining a better relationship between suppliers and buyers for long-term growth. In addition, buyer-supplier partnership and information integration significantly impact supply chain performance (Khan et al., 2015). Another study examined the quality of the relationship and supply risk mitigation on medium and large-sized manufacturing firms' supply chain performance in developing countries. This study highlights the importance of confidence and reliance in reducing supplier defaults and improving supply chain performance (Al-Shboul, 2023). Supplier involvement moderates the relationship between confidence and supply risk mitigation, positively affecting supply chain performance.

Due to the current volatile environment and fierce competition, manufacturing firms (MFs) must improve their performance to survive. In this regard, checking and monitoring the suppliers' risk should significantly improve the performance of MFs (Qiao & Zhao, 2023). In addition, a relation based on not being an opportunist, confidence and reliance are influential factors in reducing the supplier defaults on his/her supply obligations and improving supply chain performance (SCP). Besides, the moderator function of supplier involvement (SI) in the relationship between quality of the relationship (QoR) and supply risk mitigation (SRM) is undeniable. Factors such as early supplier involvement, partnership quality, trust, guanxi, confidence, reliance, and supplier involvement play pivotal roles in enhancing supply chain performance through improved collaboration, information sharing, and risk mitigation strategies (Al-Shboul, 2023; Qiao & Zhao, 2023). Likewise, effective supplier-buyer relationship management should not be seen only in terms of cost and financial measures, as outlined by Transaction cost economics, but also in terms of other ("softer") relational benefits, like more comprehensive information sharing, higher levels of trust, better cooperation and increased relationship flexibility (Rašković & Mörec, 2013).

The relationship between suppliers and buyers significantly influences supply chain performance, as highlighted by the prior literature. For example, Rašković and Mörec (2013) noted that effective supplier-buyer relationship management, encompassing aspects like information sharing, trust, cooperation, and flexibility, impacts relationship competitiveness. This, in turn, influences the overall performance and long-term competitiveness of the supply chain (Rašković & Mörec, 2013). The routines of supplier selection and evaluation, along with managerial attitudes towards relational and performance risks, play a crucial role in forming buyer-supplier partnerships. Partner selection routines positively influence firms' propensity to form partnerships, emphasizing the importance of these relationship-building processes in

enhancing supply chain performance (Gallear et al., 2021). Based on the findings of prior literature, this study hypothesized that supplier-buyer relationship would positively influence supply chain performance.

H₃: Supplier-buyer relationship positively and directly influences supply chain performance

Conceptual Model of the Study

The conceptual model of this research was established based on previous studies that used the Resource-Based View (RBV) theory and the assumptions on the factors influencing supply chain performance, drawing from both theoretical and empirical viewpoints. Figure 1 depicts the conceptual model of the study.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study
Source: Conceptualized from the Existing Literature, 2024

The Mathematical Model

The research used the mathematical equation $x = IY + e$ to demonstrate the relationships between latent variables and their observable indicators, as seen in Figure 1. The variable x denotes the observable indicator, while Y

represents the latent variable. The loading coefficient L is a statistical measure that assesses the strength of the link between the dependent observable indicator x and the independent latent variable Y . The variable e represents the random measurement error (Shatta, 2023; Sarstedt et al., 2022).

Materials and Methods

The adoption of the positivist philosophy was motivated by the need to scientifically examine the hypotheses that are inherent in the inquiry. In addition, the study included descriptive and explanatory cross-sectional survey research methodologies to collect data from a targeted cohort of purchasers and vendors. A single instance of data collection was performed, and a subset of the whole population was examined (Creswell & Plano, 2018). Similarly, this study used a survey approach to gather data, since it allows for the gathering and quantitative analysis of data using descriptive and inferential statistics. However, this research followed the tenth rule proposed by Hair et al. (2019) to calculate the optimal sample size required for testing the hypotheses of the study model using PLS-SEM and SmartPLS software.

As per Hair et al. (2019), the tenth rule of thumb suggests that the minimum sample size required to test the hypotheses of a proposed research model is ten times the maximum number of indicators for one of the exogenous constructs. This research includes four indicators for information sharing and five indicators for strategic procurement planning as exogenous constructs. Based on the tenth rule of thumb, the minimum sample size required to test the hypotheses of a proposed research model was 50 and a sample size of 167 respondents was considered sufficient for evaluating the hypotheses of this study, as it surpassed the minimum need of respondents. In addition, closed-ended questionnaires were assigned numerical values to expedite and improve the accuracy of quantitative data analysis. The gathered quantitative data for respondents' profile were analyzed using descriptive statistics with the aid of IBM SPSS Statistics Software Version 26. The hypotheses were evaluated using inferential statistical analysis, namely Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), with the use of SmartPLS 4 software. The SmartPLS 4 software used the extra response strategy to handle missing data. This study used the value of 99 as a replacement for missing values that were included in the questionnaires. Nevertheless, this method

enabled the creation of a well-defined differentiation between data that was visually seen and data that was not directly witnessed (Hair et al., 2019).

Variables and Measurement Procedures

This study emphasizes the value of variables, indicators, measurement scales, and analytical techniques and instruments in research, highlighting the intricacy and significance of taking these factors into account. The general data collected from the respondents was operationally evaluated using non-parametric measures for type of respondent, gender and educational attainment. To determine the answers to the attitude questions, a nominal scale representing "1 for buyer" and 2 for supplier. Additionally, "1 for male" and "2 for female" and, 1 for "primary education level" and 7 for "PhD level" were used. The respondents' general information was operationally measured using parametric measurements of age and experience. A ratio scale was used to assess the respondent's age and experience. The variables (independent, dependent and mediator), were evaluated using non-parametric measurements. The responses were scored using a five-point Likert scale, where 1 represented "strongly disagree" and 5 represented "strongly agree." Appendix A lists the variables, indicators, measurement level, tool, and data analysis technique.

Evaluation of Models

This research used Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) evaluation tools to analyze reflecting models. The decision was based on the attributes of the constructs and their corresponding indicators in the theoretical study model shown in Figure 3. Given that all indicators depended on their constructs, a reflective model was considered appropriate for this inquiry. The assessment of the measurement model and the structural model of the suggested research model adhered to the standards established by Hair et al. (2019). The evaluation of the reflective measurement models included many phases. Initially, the researchers assessed the reliability of the indicators, setting a criterion that the dependability value must exceed 0.708.

Furthermore, the internal consistency reliability of the composite dependability of constructs was evaluated, using a criterion of 0.708 or above. Furthermore, the convergent validity of the constructs was assessed by calculating the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value, which should exceed 0.5. Finally, the discriminant validity was evaluated by using the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations (HTMT) criteria, which should be below 0.9. Furthermore, the collinearity of the constructs in the structural model was evaluated. According to Hair et al. (2019), the VIF values should ideally be about 3 or lower.

After considering collinearity, the main variables utilized to assess the structural model in PLS-SEM were as follows: Path coefficients with a significance level, t-statistic greater than 1.96 at a significance level of 0.05 for all paths are regarded acceptable. Additionally, p-values of 0.05 or below are considered significant. The R² values of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 may be classified as statistically significant, moderately significant, and weakly significant, respectively (Hair et al., 2019). According to Hair et al. (2019), effect values of f² larger than 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 suggest minor, medium, and large impact sizes correspondingly. Moreover, all constructs exhibited a composite reliability (CR) that above the threshold of 0.708, and their average variance extracted (AVE) values were all over 0.5. According to these results, each construct explained more than 50 percent of the variability in the indicator, which suggests that the item's dependability is good (Hair et al., 2019). Overall, the evaluation results for both the measurement and structural models were deemed good and met all the criteria established by Hair et al. (2019) (See appendix B).

Ultimately, you should explain how you studied the problem, identify the procedures you followed, and structure this information as logically as possible.

If your methods are new, you'll need to explain them in detail. If they've been published before, cite the original work, including your amendments if you've made modifications. Identify the equipment and the materials you

Results

Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

The data presented in Table 1 provides information on the gender, age group, education, experience, and kind of respondents. Approximately 64 percent of the respondents were male, while approximately 36 percent were female. Furthermore, the majority of the participants were in the age range of 31 to 50 years, accounting for around 78 percent. Additionally, around 84 percent of the respondents had a bachelor's or master's degree. Conversely, over 60 percent of the participants were buyers, while roughly 40 percent were suppliers who had accumulated expertise in the industry, ranging from 1 to 20 years, making up about 90 percent of the total. These findings align with the outcomes of previous research. For instance, a research conducted by bin Aqdas et al. (2023) found that 88 percent of the participants were male, while 12 percent were female. In a similar vein, the research conducted by bin Aqdas et al. (2023) shown that 78 percent of the participants were between the age range of 30 to 49.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents (n=167)

Characteristics		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	107	64.1
	Female	60	35.9
Age Group	21-30	25	15.0
	31-40	80	47.9
	41-50	50	29.9

	51-60	10	6.0
	61+	2	1.2
Education	Certificate Level	5	3.0
	Diploma Level	21	12.6
	Bachelor Degree	104	62.3
	Master's Degree	37	22.1
Kind of Resp.	Buyer	100	59.9
	Supplier	67	40.1
Experience	1-10	100	59.9
	11-20	50	29.9
	21-30	10	6.0
	31+	7	4.2

Indicator's Reliabilities, R2 and Relevance of the Path Coefficients

Figure 2 shows the loadings (reliabilities) of all indicators for the constructs obtained by using the PLS-SEM approach with the aid of SmartPLS 4. Most of these loadings were found to exceed the recommended threshold of 0.708, as proposed by Hair et al. (2019). In addition, R² values were 0.458 and 0.583, respectively which implied that strategic procurement planning (SPP) and information sharing (IS) had a significant influence on 45.8 percent of the variance in the supplier-buyer relationship

(SBR). Moreover, the research revealed that a considerable proportion of 58.3 percent of the variance in the supply chain performance (SCP) may be attributed to the collective impact of strategic procurement planning (SPP) and information sharing (IS), in aggregation with the supplier-buyer relationship (SBR). Furthermore, all suggested links exhibited positive path coefficients, signifying that a one standard deviation increase in the exogenous constructs of strategic procurement planning (SPP) and information sharing (IS), along with the mediator supplier-buyer relationship (SBR), led to an increase in the supply chain performance.

Figure 2. Indicator's Reliabilities, R2 Values and Relevance of the Path Coefficients

Reliability and Convergent Validity Analysis Results

Hair et al. (2019) determined that a construct is reliable if its composite reliability (CR) score exceeds 0.708. Furthermore, for a construct to have convergent validity, its Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value must be greater than 0.5. This study assessed the reliability of all constructs by calculating their composite reliability (CR), which were found to be greater than 0.708. Furthermore, the convergent validity of all constructs was evaluated using the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value, which was greater than 0.5. The findings show that this study identified positive response patterns, with each component helping to explain the variation in its corresponding item (Hair et al., 2019). Table 2 shows the reliability and validity of the constructs used in the study.

Table 2. The Reliability and Validity Values of the Constructs

	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Information Sharing (IS)	0.904	0.702
Strategic Procurement Planning (SPP)	0.849	0.533
Supplier-Buyer Relationship (SBR)	0.944	0.773
Supply Chain Performance (SCP)	0.942	0.669

Discriminant Validity Analysis (HTMT Results)

According to Table 3, the HTMT values for all of the research model's examined influences were below 0.90. According to the results, the study model's components of this study were empirically distinct from one another, just as Hair et al. (2019) had predicted.

Table 3. Discriminant Validity Analysis (HTMT Results)

Construct	Information Sharing (IS)	Strategic Procurement Planning (SPP)	Supplier-Buyer Relationship (SBR)
Strategic Procurement Planning (SPP)	0.658		
Supplier-Buyer Relationship (SBR)	0.651	0.705	
Supply Chain Performance (SCP)	0.540	0.723	0.819

F² Values Results

According to the study by Hair et al. (2019), small, medium, and large f^2 values are 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 impact sizes, respectively. Effect sizes (f^2) of 0.170, 0.215, and 1.398 were discovered during the study's analysis for each unique connection, as shown in Table 4. Based on these results, it was confirmed that all of the research model's hypotheses of this study had medium and large effect sizes as recommended by Hair et al. (2019).

Table 4. F² Values Results

	Supplier-Buyer Relationship (SBR)	Supply Chain Performance (SCP)
Information Sharing (IS)	0.170	
Strategic Procurement Planning (SPP)	0.215	
Supplier-Buyer Relationship (SBR)		1.398

Table 6. Direct and Indirect Statistical Significance Results of the Hypotheses

Hypothesis	Influence	STDEV	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
IS -> SBR	Direct	0.077	4.740	0.000
IS -> SBR ->SCP	Indirect	0.065	4.251	0.000
SPP -> SBR	Direct	0.068	6.012	0.000
SPP -> SBR -> SCP	Indirect	0.050	6.182	0.000
SBR -> SCP	Direct	0.035	21.795	0.000

Importance-Performance Map Analysis Results

Figure 4. Importance-Performance Map Analysis Results

The construct ‘supplier-buyer relationship (SBR)’ shown in Figure 4 is positioned above the average level of importance and performance of the target construct ‘supply chain performance (SCP)’. The rationale for this positioning is that it emphasizes the need of prioritizing and allocating more resources to enhance the supplier-buyer relationship (SBR) in order to improve supply chain performance (SCP). Nevertheless, the constructs ‘strategic procurement planning (SPP)’ and ‘information sharing (IS)’ are considered less important in improving the construct ‘supply chain

performance (SCP)’ because they are positioned below the average of importance. These findings indicate that strategic procurement planning (SPP) and information sharing (IS) have a restricted impact on supply chain performance (SCP). However, these constructs are positioned above the average on the performance map of the construct ‘supply chain performance (SCP)’. This suggests that they are also significant in enhancing the supply chain performance (SCP).

Discussion

The Hypotheses Tested

This research posited that the implementation of strategic procurement planning would have a direct impact on the relationship between suppliers and buyers, while also having an indirect effect on the overall performance of the supply chain. The findings from Figure 2, Figure 3 and Table 2 indicated that there were positive path coefficients. This means that a one standard deviation improvement in strategic procurement planning resulted in an increase in both the supplier-buyer relationship and supply chain performance, and vice versa. Furthermore, the findings validated a statistically significant level of both direct and indirect impacts ($p < 0.05$). These findings confirm the presence of the expected correlations in actual life. Furthermore, these findings support the conclusions of earlier studies (Masanta & Ochiri, 2016; Nkrumah et al., 2019) that demonstrate the significant impact of strategic procurement planning on supply chain performance. This impact is achieved through the improvement of productivity, project performance, and procurement outcomes within organizations,

facilitated by practices such as strategic sourcing, supplier evaluation, and procurement planning.

Similarly, this research forecasted that the act of sharing information would have a direct impact on the relationship between suppliers and buyers, while also indirectly affecting the overall performance of the supply chain. The findings from Figure 2, Figure 3 and Table 2 indicated that there were positive path coefficients, suggesting that a one standard deviation rise in information sharing would result in the enhancement of the supplier-buyer relationship, as well as an advancement in the supply chain performance. Similarly, the results from this research demonstrate that information sharing has a statistically significant valuable effect (p value < 0.05) on both the supplier-buyer relationship and supply chain performance. The findings of this study align with the conclusions of prior research conducted by Baah et al. (2021), bin Aqdas et al. (2023), Alhamda et al. (2023), Joensuu-Salo & Sorama (2019), and Owot et al. (2023). These studies have demonstrated that the act of sharing information is vital in improving supply chain performance through the enhancement of visibility, collaboration, agility, and partner relationships.

Moreover, this research postulated that the relationship between the supplier and buyer would have a direct impact on the performance of the supply chain. The findings shown in Figure 2, Figure 3 and Table 2 confirmed a favourable path coefficient, suggesting that a one standard deviation rise in the supplier-buyer relationship would result in an enhancement of the supply chain performance. Likewise, the findings indicate that the relationship between suppliers and buyers has a statistically significant beneficial influence (p value < 0.05) on the performance of the supply chain. On the other hand, the findings of this study are consistent with other prior studies (Khan et al., 2022; Al-Shboul, 2023; Khan et al., 2015; Qiao & Zhao, 2023; Rašković & Mörec, 2013; Gallear et al., 2021; Park & Lee, 2018) that have shown the importance of the supplier-buyer relationship in impacting the performance of the supply chain.

Theoretical Implications

This study has successfully addressed the need for a specific model that clarifies the factors influencing supply chain performance through the intermediary of the supplier-buyer relationship. This particular paradigm is absent from the current body of theoretical literature. The research has focused on analyzing the influence of the supplier-buyer relationship as a mediator, as well as the predictive factors of strategic procurement planning and information sharing on the supplier-buyer relationship and supply chain performance. The study employs the Resource-Based View (RBV) framework, which currently lacks a specific model for studying both tangible and intangible resources within an organization.

Practical Implications

The verified model indicates that the relationship between suppliers and buyers has a mediating impact on the performance of the supply chain. The findings suggest that strategic procurement planning and information sharing play a crucial role in improving supply chain performance by influencing the relationship between suppliers and buyers. The statistical significance of strategic procurement planning and information sharing in both direct and indirect influences suggests that buyers and suppliers depend on these practices to enhance supply chain performance.

Conclusion

The results shown in Figure 4 offers concrete evidence that supports the accuracy of the research model offered in the context of decision-making, particularly in terms of prioritizing investments to enhance supply chain performance.

Limitation and Recommendation for Future Research

This research used a limited range of resources of an organization, namely "strategic procurement planning, information sharing, and

supplier-buyer relationship" derived from the Resource-Based View (RBV), to forecast the enhancement of supply chain performance. The combination of these components accounted for 58.3% of the observed variation in the supply chain performance, as seen in Figure 3. The present study suggests that future research should include more components from the Resource-Based View (RBV). It is advisable to use this strategy to improve the diversity in the performance of the supply chain and to expand the applicability of the validated model. Moreover, this research only employed Tanzanian buyers and suppliers as participants. It is suggested that future research should include suppliers and buyers from several countries in order to enhance the generalizability of the proposed model for forecasting the factors that influence supply chain performance.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors have no conflict of interest.

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